

Quadratic Kernel Learning for Interpolation Kernel Machine Based Graph Classification

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Abstract. Interpolating classifiers interpolate all the training data and thus have zero training error. Recent research shows their fundamental importance for high-performance ensemble techniques. Interpolation kernel machines belong to the class of interpolating classifiers and do generalize well. They have been demonstrated to be a good alternative to support vector machine for graph classification. In this work we further improve their performance by considering multiple kernel learning. We establish a general scheme for achieving this goal. The current experimental work is done using quadratic kernel combination. Our experimental results demonstrate the performance boosting potential of our approach against the use of individual graph kernels.

1 Introduction

There are a large amount of data that can be modeled naturally as graphs. They appear in many application domains, ranging from social networks to chemistry and medicine. Graph classification can be applied to such data for answering numerous challenging questions [11,13,22]. For instance, chemical compounds can be modeled as graphs where vertices correspond to atoms and edges to bonds. Then, graph classification helps predict if a compound is active, say against HIV or if a protein is an enzyme or not. The datasets used in our experimental work as described in Section 4 give concrete examples of applications.

Graph kernels provide a way to compute similarities between graphs and have been studied for a long time, e.g. for graph classification. Dozens of graph kernels have been developed [11,13,22], which focus on specific structural properties of graphs. The key design ideas behind these graph kernels differ, e.g. based on Weisfeiler-Lehman test of graph isomorphism [24], paths [4], and graph decomposition [17]. Meanwhile, public graph kernel libraries are also available [10,25].

Despite the diversity in the design of graph kernels, their use for classification is, however, rather monotonous and dominated by support vector machines (SVM). This is clearly reflected in the recent survey papers for graph kernels

[11,13,22], e.g. “The criteria used for prediction are SVM for classification” [11]. This is not a surprise due to the dominance of SVM in machine learning.

As another kernel-based classification method, interpolation kernel machines belong to the class of interpolating classifiers that interpolate all the training data and thus have zero training error [27]. The study [3] demonstrated that interpolation kernel machines trained to have zero training error do perform very well on test data (a phenomenon typically observed in over-parametrized deep learning models). Our recent work [30] has shown that interpolation kernel machines are a good alternative to SVM for graph classification. This study justifies a systematic consideration of interpolation kernel machines parallel to the popular SVM for experimentation in graph classification. For this purpose we have proposed an extended experimental protocol in [30] to obtain the maximal possible graph classification performance in a particular application.

In this work we further improve the performance of interpolation kernel machines by considering multiple kernel learning [5]. We establish a general scheme for achieving this goal. The current experimental work is done using quadratic kernel combination. Our experimental results demonstrate the performance boosting potential of our approach.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. We give a brief general discussion of interpolating classifiers and introduce interpolation kernel machines in Section 2. The general scheme of multiple kernel learning tailored to interpolation kernel machines is presented in Section 3. The experimental results follow in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Interpolating classifiers

It is commonly believed that perfectly fitting the training data, as in the case of interpolating classifiers, must inevitably lead to overfitting. Recent research, however, reveals good reasons to study such classifiers. For instance, the work [27] provides strong indications that ensemble techniques are particularly successful if they are built on interpolating classifiers. A prominent example is random forest. Recently, Belkin [2] emphasizes the importance of interpolation (and its sibling over-parametrization) to understand the foundations of deep learning.

2.1 Interpolation kernel machines

Here we introduce a technique to fully interpolate the training data using kernel functions, known as kernel machines [3,9]. Note that this term has been often used in research papers (e.g. [8,29]), where variants of support vector machines are effectively meant. For the sake of clarity we will use the term “interpolation kernel machine” throughout the paper.

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \subset \Omega^n$ be a set of n training samples with their corresponding targets $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\} \subset \mathcal{T}^n$ in the target space. The sets are sorted so that the corresponding training sample and target have the same

index. A function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ interpolates this data iif:

$$f(x_i) = y_i, \quad \forall i \in 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Representer Theorem Let $k : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive semidefinite kernel for some domain Ω , X and Y a set of training samples and targets as defined above, and $g : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a strictly monotonically increasing function for regularization. We define E as an error function that calculates the loss L of f on the whole sample set with:

$$E(X, Y) = E((x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L(f(x_i), y_i) + g(\|f\|) \quad (2)$$

Then, the function $f^* = \operatorname{argmin}_f \{E(X, Y)\}$ that minimizes the error E has the form:

$$f^*(z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(z, x_i) \quad \text{with } \alpha_i \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3)$$

The proof can be found in many textbooks, e.g. [6].

We now can use f^* from Eq. (3) to interpolate our training data. Note that the only learnable parameters are $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$, a real-valued vector with the same length as the number of training samples. Learning α is equivalent to solving the system of linear equations:

$$G(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (4)$$

where $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the kernel (Gram) matrix. In case of positive definite kernel k the Gram matrix G is invertible. Therefore, we can find the optimal α^* to construct f^* by:

$$(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = G^{-1}(y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (5)$$

After learning, the interpolation kernel machine then uses the interpolating function from Eq. (3) to make prediction for test samples. Note that solving the optimal parameters α^* in (5) in a naive manner requires computation of order $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ and is thus not feasible for large-scale applications. A highly efficient solver EigenPro has been developed [15] to enable significant speedup for training on GPUs. Another recent work [26] applies an explainable AI technique for sample condensation of interpolation kernel machines.

In this work we focus on classification problems. In this case $f(z)$ is encoded as a one-hot vector $f(z) = (f_1(z), \dots, f_c(z))$ with $c \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of output classes. This requires c times repeating the learning process above, one for each component of the one-hot vector. This computation can be formulated as follows. Let $A_l = (\alpha_{l1}^*, \dots, \alpha_{ln}^*)$ be the parameters to be learned and $Y_l = (y_{l1}, \dots, y_{ln})$ target values for each component $l = 1, \dots, c$. The learning of interpolation kernel machine becomes:

$$G \underbrace{(A_1^T, \dots, A_c^T)}_A = \underbrace{(Y_1^T, \dots, Y_c^T)}_Y \quad (6)$$

with the unique solution:

$$A = G^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (7)$$

which is the extended version of Eq. (5) for c classes and results in zero error on training data. When predicting a test sample z , the output vector $f(z)$ is not a probability vector in general. The class which gets the highest output value is considered as the predicted class. If needed, e.g. for the purpose of classifier combination, the output vector (z) can also be converted into a probability vector by applying the softmax function.

3 Multiple kernel learning for interpolation kernel machines

Multiple kernel learning (MKL) methods use multiple kernels simultaneously instead of selecting one specific kernel function [5]. Given a pool of m kernels k_i , $i = 1, \dots, m$, a combined kernel function is generally defined by:

$$\Phi(K = (k_1, \dots, k_m), W)$$

where W are the weights (parameters) for kernel combination. Applications for MKL have been found, for instance, in processing biomedical data [16,23]. Recent developments include extensions to handle the scenario with missing channels in data [14] and unreliable data [1]. For graph classification, it was proposed to use a linear combination of kernel matrices obtained from the same kernel with different values of the hyper-parameters [18]. The recent work [28] deals with MKL using a GMDH-type neural network. In both [18,28] the classification backbone is SVM.

3.1 Construction of combined kernels

Positive definite kernels can be combined to build more complex positive definite kernels. Given two such kernels k_1 and k_2 , some simple combination rules are:

- $k(x, y) = c \cdot k_1(x, y)$, for all $c \in \mathbb{R}_+$
- $k(x, y) = k_1(x, y) + c$, for all $c \in \mathbb{R}_+$
- $k(x, y) = k_1(x, y) + k_2(x, y)$
- $k(x, y) = k_1(x, y) \cdot k_2(x, y)$
- $k(x, y) = f(x) \cdot f(y)$ for any function f mapping to \mathbb{R}

The proof and additional combination rules can be found in [6]. The fundamental discussion in the following applies to any combined kernel $\Phi(K, W)$ that are constructed using such rules to guarantee the positive definiteness. Obviously, polynomial functions satisfy this requirement. This work will focus on quadratic combination only:

$$\Phi_q(K, W) = w_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot k_i + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=i}^m w_{ij} \cdot k_i k_j$$

with the weights $W = (w_0, w_1, \dots, w_m, w_{11}, w_{12}, \dots, w_{1m}, \dots, w_{mm})$, $|W| = (m+1)(m+2)/2$.

The weights W can be constrained in different ways. In this work we study three variants: \mathbb{R} (no constraint), \mathbb{R}_+^0 (nonnegative), $[0, 1]$. When using nonnegative weights, we can extract and study the relative importance of the terms of combined kernels [5]. The interval $[0, 1]$ further restricts the influence of these terms.

3.2 General scheme of MKL for interpolation kernel machines

We present a general scheme (formulation and solution) of MKL tailored to interpolation kernel machines. Given the pool of kernels K , the combined kernel results in Gram matrix $G(W)$ that is built on $\Phi(K, W)$ and thus dependent of the weights W . Then, the task of learning an interpolation kernel machine becomes:

$$\min_{W, A} E(W, A) = \min_{W, A} \|G(W)A - Y\|^2 \quad (8)$$

with $|W| + cn$ parameters to be optimally estimated.

Due to $|W| \ll cn$, this optimization problem is dominated by estimating the large number of parameters of the interpolation kernel machine. A parameter decomposition technique has been discussed in [12] for effective parameter reduction (see Appendix for a brief summary) and found applications [19,32]. For applying this technique, we can naturally partition all parameters into two groups: W and A . Then, the optimization problem can be reformulated as:

$$\min_{W, A} E(W, A) = \min_W \left[\min_A \|G(W)A - Y\|^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

$$= \min_W \Psi(W) = \min_W G(W)^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (10)$$

where $\Psi(W)$ means the global minimum of the overall optimization function for a fixed W and all possibilities of A . The last step is justified by the fact that for a fixed W , we simply need to search for the optimal interpolation kernel machine for the concrete combined kernel $\Phi(K, W)$. When following the construction rules above, the combined kernel is guaranteed to remain positive definite. Thus, the corresponding Gram matrix $G(W)$ is invertible and the interpolation kernel machine deduced from $\Phi(K, W)$ has a unique solution, see Eq. (7). Doing it this way, we are able to reduce the number of optimization parameters from $|W| + cn$ to $|W|$ only without any loss of optimization quality.

In practice, however, the optimization scheme (10) does not work because of a specific property of interpolating classifiers, as an interpolation kernel machine is. The optimization function $E(W, A)$ is simply insensitive to W . Whatever value W is assumed to take, the interpolation kernel machine deduced from the combined kernel $\Phi(K, W)$ will produce zero training error, i.e. $\Psi(W) = 0$ holds for all W . Pragmatically, we thus introduce an approximation in order to make the optimization function $E(W, A)$ workable. For this purpose the original optimization task (8) is reformulated using the two-step (alternating) optimization method [5]:

- Step 1: We optimize A by using (fixing) the current W :

$$\min_A \|G(W)A - Y\|^2$$

This corresponds to solving the standard problem of learning an interpolation kernel machine for the combined kernel $\Phi(K, W)$.

- Step 2: We optimize W by using (fixing) the current A :

$$\min_W \|G(W)A - Y\|^2$$

- We repeat the two steps until convergence.

In both steps the minimization is done using the complete training dataset. This is exactly the reason for the trouble discussed above. Thus, we introduce a simple heuristic to circumvent the problem. We partition the training dataset T into two subsets: $T = T_1 \cup T_2$, $T_1 \cap T_2 = \emptyset$. Then, we use T_1 for step 1 and T_2 for step 2. In this work T_1 is chosen to contain 80% and T_2 20% of the training data, respectively.

3.3 Dealing with indefinite kernels

Learning interpolation kernel machines as presented in Section 2.1 requires positive definite kernels. In practice, however, many kernels reported in the literature, do not satisfy this property. This is particularly the case when working with graph kernels. Combining indefinite kernels generally does not deliver positive definite kernels. Thus, we need an indefinite interpolation kernel machine learning method for step 1 of the two-step optimization. Several methods for such an extension have been studied in [31]. We will use the matrix perturbation method in this work. The trouble with indefinite kernels is the lacking invertibility of the Gram matrix G . The matrix perturbation method artificially introduces some minor perturbation (noise) to G to make it invertible.

4 Experimental results

We use 18 graph datasets from various domains (see Table 1 for an overview). These datasets have different application background. Examples of chemical datasets include benzodiazepine receptor dataset (BZR), cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors (COX2), inhibitors of dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), estrogen receptor ligands (ERMD). They are classified whether the chemical composition is active. Several datasets are related to medical applications. For instance, the AIDS dataset contains chemical compounds which have been screened as active or inactive against HIV. The Proteins dataset is for protein function prediction (functional class membership of enzymes and non-enzymes). The PTC (Predictive Toxicity Challenge) dataset is labeled according to carcinogenicity on rodents, aiming to predict carcinogenicity of chemical compounds. The Cuneiform dataset contains graphs representing different Hittite cuneiform signs. MSRC_9

Table 1: Description of graph datasets.

domain	dataset	# graphs	# classes	avg. # nodes	avg. # edges
Chemistry	BZR	405	2	35.8	38.4
	BZR_MD	306	2	21.3	225.1
	COX2	467	2	41.2	43.5
	COX2_MD	303	2	26.3	335.1
	DHFR	467	2	42.4	44.5
	DHFR_MD	393	2	23.87	283.01
	ER_MD	446	2	21.3	234.9
	MUTAG	188	2	17.9	19.8
Medicine	AIDS	2000	2	15.69	16.20
	PROTEINS	1113	2	39.1	72.8
	PROTEIN_full	1113	2	39.1	72.8
	PTC_FM	349	2	14.1	14.5
	PTC_FR	351	2	14.6	15.0
	PTC_MM	336	2	14.0	14.3
	PTC_MR	344	2	14.3	14.7
	Vision	Cuneiform	267	30	21.3
MSRC_9		221	8	40.6	97.9
MSRC_21		563	20	77.5	198.3

and MSRC.21 are datasets in semantic image processing. Semantic labels are, for instance, building, grass, tree, cow, sky, sheep, boat, face, car, bicycle, etc.

Six graph kernels were selected for the experiments: shortest-path kernel [4], neighborhood hash kernel [7], Weisfeiler-Lehman graph kernel [24], tree-based graph decomposition kernel [17], propagation kernel [20], and pyramid match kernel [21]. The main selection criterion are the diverse design paradigms of these kernels. We used the implementations from the graph kernel library GraKeL written in Python [25]. For each pair of dataset and graph kernel, we conducted a 5-fold cross validation and report the average performance in term of classification accuracy.

The results on these datasets are presented in Table 2, where matrix perturbation was used for achieving positive definiteness. For each dataset the best-performing method is shown in bold. The quadratic kernel learning (QKL) considerably improves the performance (classification accuracy) of the individual graph kernels. In particular, restricting the weights to a small interval $[0, 1]$ turns out to be positive. The matrix perturbation method, however, is not best-performing among the methods studied in [31] to deal with indefinite kernels. Instead, a cross-entropy variant proved to be most favorable. Table 3 shows the superior performance of this variant compared with matrix perturbation on the individual graph kernels. Unfortunately, it is not possible to apply this variant in step 1 of the two-step optimization to replace matrix perturbation (the reason for this is rather technical and thus not detailed here). Nevertheless, we show a

Table 2: Accuracy (%) of individual graph kernels (matrix perturbation was used for achieving positive definiteness) and quadratic kernel learning.

method dataset	Shortest Path	Neighborhood Hash	Weisfeiler Lehman	Graph Decomposition	Propagation	Pyramid Match	QKL (\mathbb{R})	QKL (\mathbb{R}_+^0)	QKL ($[0,1]$)
BZR	70.1	87.9	83.9	85.7	70.4	67.9	84.9	86.4	86.7
BZR_MD	52.2	52.9	49.0	57.2	52.3	59.8	63.7	67.6	68.6
COX2	65.5	79.7	68.3	78.8	65.5	64.9	79.4	81.1	81.2
COX2_MD	60.7	48.2	52.5	53.8	53.4	55.8	60.7	63.0	64.7
DHFR	51.6	71.4	70.4	79.4	53.3	49.3	75.9	78.8	79.9
DHFR_MD	62.9	56.5	62.9	62.4	56.8	56.5	64.7	68.7	68.5
ER_MD	52.2	54.3	61.4	54.7	60.1	58.5	61.4	64.3	69.7
MUTAG	63.8	79.9	84.1	82.5	56.5	79.9	78.2	83.5	84.6
AIDS	63.5	94.6	81.7	52.5	49.3	66.2	99.1	99.6	99.5
PROTEINS	55.2	64.5	64.7	57.1	54.9	55.3	74.8	75.1	75.5
PROTEINS_full	57.3	63.4	64.8	55.6	58.9	57.8	76.4	76.5	76.5
PTC_FM	59.8	54.4	59.3	57.7	52.2	55.6	65.3	65.3	66.2
PTC_FR	60.4	61.8	62.7	62.7	52.1	61.0	63.3	64.1	64.1
PTC_MM	55.0	58.9	64.3	57.5	52.7	55.4	63.1	63.1	63.7
PTC_MR	54.4	57.9	54.7	59.0	52.9	57.3	62.2	61.0	61.6
Cuneiform	19.2	46.9	52.5	21.2	55.0	78.1	77.4	82.1	80.4
MSRC_9	51.5	92.8	90.1	85.9	90.5	92.3	95.5	94.6	94.2
MSRC_21	59.3	91.5	87.6	64.9	87.9	90.4	91.5	91.8	91.8
average	56.4	67.6	67.5	62.7	59.7	64.6	74.3	75.9	76.5

Table 3: Accuracy (%) of individual graph kernels (a cross-entropy variant was used to deal with indefinite kernels) and quadratic kernel learning.

method dataset	Shortest Path	Neighborhood Hash	Weisfeiler Lehman	Graph Decomposition	Propagation	Pyramid Match	QKL ([0,1])
BZR	84.9	87.8	86.2	85.7	84.0	85.0	86.4
BZR_MD	68.9	66.7	58.5	62.7	57.8	59.8	70.9
COX2	79.7	79.7	81.0	78.8	80.1	80.5	82.0
COX2_MD	61.4	59.7	60.1	62.4	55.1	55.8	66.3
DHFR	75.7	82.5	79.6	79.4	75.9	77.4	79.7
DHFR_MD	67.2	60.4	64.4	67.9	60.5	56.5	69.5
ER_MD	62.8	69.3	67.7	54.7	67.7	58.5	69.9
MUTAG	78.8	84.6	79.8	82.5	74.5	87.2	84.6
AIDS	97.5	99.2	92.5	81.2	85.4	99.2	99.5
PROTEINS	74.9	73.7	68.5	65.4	68.9	73.9	75.9
PROTEINS_full	75.9	71.9	68.9	65.8	68.6	74.2	76.5
PTC_FM	60.7	58.5	67.0	62.2	61.6	59.9	65.6
PTC_FR	64.4	68.4	67.5	66.4	66.4	63.0	64.4
PTC_MM	63.7	67.9	67.0	66.1	68.5	63.7	62.8
PTC_MR	59.3	63.4	64.2	61.0	57.3	59.6	60.7
Cuneiform	70.7	71.7	81.5	75.4	81.8	78.1	80.4
MSRC_9	91.0	92.8	90.1	85.9	91.4	92.3	95.2
MSRC_21	59.3	91.5	87.6	64.9	82.4	90.4	92.3
average	72.0	75.0	74.0	70.5	71.6	73.1	76.8

comparison with these results in Table 3. Here the quadratic kernel learning is still favorable.

5 Conclusion

Interpolation kernel machines have been demonstrated to be a good alternative to support vector machine for graph classification. In this work we further improve their performance by considering multiple kernel learning. We have presented a general scheme for achieving this goal. Our experimental results using quadratic kernel combination demonstrated the performance boosting potential of our approach against the use of individual graph kernels. In future we will study more complex combined kernels. In addition, we will also apply the proposed general scheme to non-graph data. With interpolation kernel machines as an alternative to support vector machine our work contributes to increasing the methodological plurality in the graph processing community (and beyond).

Appendix: Parameter decomposition for function fitting

In contrast to treating all parameters simultaneously the parameters are decomposed into two parts, one part can be solved by either an analytic or a direct method, and the other part has to be solved by an iterative optimization process. Let \mathbf{p}_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, denote n data points to be fitted by function $f(\mathbf{v}) = 0$, where $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ is the parameter vector. Given the distance function $d(\mathbf{p}_i, f(\mathbf{v}))$ of a point \mathbf{p}_i to $f(\mathbf{v})$, the geometric fitting problem can be formulated as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^k} \sum_{i=1}^n d(\mathbf{p}_i, f(\mathbf{v}))$$

We decompose \mathbf{v} into $\mathbf{v} = [\mathbf{v}_1 \mathbf{v}_2]$, where $\mathbf{v}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{k_1}$, $\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{k_2}$, and $k \equiv k_1 + k_2$. After a rearrangement of parameters \mathbf{v} , the optimization task becomes:

$$\min_{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^k} \sum_{i=1}^n d(\mathbf{p}_i, f(\mathbf{v})) = \min_{\mathbf{v}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{k_1}} \left[\min_{\mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{k_2}} \sum_{i=1}^n d(\mathbf{p}_i, f(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2)) \right] = \min_{\mathbf{v}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{k_1}} \Psi(\mathbf{v}_1)$$

where $\Psi(\mathbf{v}_1)$ means the global minimum sum of the distance measures for a fixed \mathbf{v}_1 and all possibilities of \mathbf{v}_2 . Assume that the optimal \mathbf{v}_2 for reaching $\Psi(\mathbf{v}_1)$ can be solved analytically or in some other way, then the original optimization problem with a total of $k_1 + k_2$ parameters is transformed into an equivalent optimization problem with k_1 parameters only. This parameter reduction can be expected to decrease the number of local minima and thus reduce the possibilities of dropping into local minima. Moreover, this scheme also tends to reduce the computation time.

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